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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTEGRATION IN EDUCATION: EMBRACING CURRICULAR REFORM AND CHANGE”

The development of artificial intelligence technologies, once a dream, has now become a reality, and every person in society feels the convenience of their usefulness. As education modernizes its methods and strategies, tools and other media become daily companions in every classroom. The higher learning institutions have innovated and adapted AI in their curricula, towards a digitally oriented classroom where teaching becomes flexible and bound in the cyber world.

Using AI in 21st-century education becomes more tangible and futuristic, where children are equipped with skills and knowledge to be more adaptable and resilient to the changing times. Education becomes irrelevant and inefficient to those who are living in difficult situations where access to these technologies is limited. During the 20th century, AI was only a fabric of education itself. As the time changed, the current situation explores ways in which AI can be utilized and adopted in education, revisiting some of its positive features together with drawbacks, and finally, to secure a learning environment both technologically advanced and also more humane.

AI in Education and Its Current Application

The mode of teaching in the academe was affected by the current application of AI in the curricula, which gives more learning opportunities for the students to explore the new trends in technology. The following AI applications that the academe must consider.

- A. **Personal Adaptive AI Learning Application** – many AI applications that could provide help to students who want to explore in support of their studies. These are the DreamBox, Knewton and Coursera. These technologies speed up the lessons for better understanding among students. Example: DreamBox Learning Platform is designed to teach mathematics from kindergarten to middle school. Knewton, is an adaptive learning platform that personalizes the learning experience of the students. It analyzes the students' performance and its weaknesses. Coursera, on the other hand, is an online learning platform that offers courses, certifications and even a degree program.
- B. **Smart Tutoring System** – is an AI system that provides tutoring. The system provides necessary lessons based on the subjects that the students find difficult. It provides topics arranged in a logical order with corresponding time allotted and explains them one by one, which makes it easier for the

student to understand. If the student makes mistakes in each choice, the system will provide the corresponding correct answer. This system can be utilized anytime and anywhere.

- C. Automatic Administrative Work** – is a digital tool, software, and automated system that handles office routines, repetitive and rule-based school tasks, or administrative work without manual interventions during operations. These will reduce workloads and minimize human error, which has always been experienced. One of the common AI's is the CHATBOTS and Virtual Assistants. Chatbots simulate human conversation through text or voice. These are usually used in digital marketing queries or product information that is essential in dealing with products.
- D. Diagnostic Prediction System** – is a machine learning and data analytics system that predicts, identifies, and assesses outcomes. In academe, it uses AI software in evaluating students' performance, such as grades. These data are stored and analyzed to determine the status of each student in their grading or in the semester. These data are transformed into students' performance records and give corresponding predictions on their achievements in the classroom. Those who failed the task receive recommendations for immediate help, such as tutoring and study counselling.

Curricular Contributions of Artificial Intelligence in Education

The contributions of artificial Intelligence in the curriculum give to the learners, teachers, and schools a new era of setup in the learning process. Teachers never teach but facilitate learning inside the classroom. Students can venture and do schooling anywhere they want to.

Below are the examples of the benefits of artificial intelligence in education;

- A. Equal and Inclusive Opportunities** – using AI in the curriculum gives equal opportunities to those who are having problems adjusting to their schooling. It also expands the coping mechanism for those children who are handicapped and have problems with the demands of the classroom tasks. AI provides help for those who are impaired, such as those with hearing or other disabilities, like the speech-to-text AI software for the deaf. Software engineers designed programs that are friendly-users and are suitable for any students who will use it for their daily activities.
- B. Data Driven Decision Making** – integrating AI in education provides a wide range of uses, especially in decision making based on the results of the student's performance, which are compiled and stored into data. These data are analyzed according to the inputs; for example, the Turnitin Draft Coach can provide actual writing analyses on the articles being submitted by the students. These will help teachers determine the true information about the result of the given task. These will also provide insights into what areas the students are doing well and failing to cope with.
- C. Ease of Work for the Teaching Staff** – ease of burden among teaching staff of having more tasks inside the classroom was lessened due to the automation of work, like quiz correction software, attendance monitoring, and a performance task monitoring system. It also provides teachers with tools in preparing lessons in a logical form. AI gives directions on how the lesson should be taught and assessed.
- D. Access to Learning Globally** – more flexible time was introduced to students as integration of AI in education progresses. Students can learn through an online platform that can be accessed worldwide. Students can choose whatever learning style they want. For example, students from other countries can enroll in a university in another country without physically being present in that learning

institution. The advent of internet and other AI tools in education gives more access to students, even to those who are living in remote areas and some disadvantaged communities.

Artificial Intelligence in Education Challenges and Ethical Considerations

The introduction of artificial intelligence in education faces problems that must be resolved.

- **Data Privacy and Security** – Protecting sensitive information is very important; it must be kept in secret; otherwise, the safety of the students could be compromised. The question lies in how secure the data is so that no one can grab it during a search on the internet.
- **Free from Algorithmic Bias** – among the unexpected consequences of using AI technology may be the spread of inequality, which becomes hard to rectify. For example, predictive systems might set aside the potential of students from disadvantaged backgrounds.
- **Neglected Learning of Students in the Physical Classroom** – physical classroom will now empty, thus become obsolete and no longer used in students' learning interactions between their teachers. Lessons will become computer-aided and mechanized without the need of physical interactions with teachers. Students become hooked with the technology, thus neglecting peer interactions and friendships.
- **Teacher Preparedness** – old generation teachers lack the necessary skills to incorporate AI into their teaching strategies, which makes it hard for them to meet the demands of rapid technological change. The academe should provide training for those teachers who will supplement learning about AI tools integration in the curricula.
- **Equal Access to Technology** – digital technology must be accessible equally, especially to those in remote areas where internet and electricity are scarce. The lack of internet connectivity, computer devices, and electricity became a stumbling block that hinders the AI integration in the classroom. It separates vulnerable learners from AI-powered opportunities, which affects student learning.

In Summary

Artificial intelligence started to create a rapid change in education as the learning process progresses. The personalized learning style through online learning improves administration task efficiencies and enables data-driven decision-making. There are issues identified, such as ethics, accessibility and teacher integration in AI inclusion to education, but those can be addressed through smart planning, professional development and equal policies of the school.

By using AI tools in education and through planning, it ensures that students are more diverse in their learning and become more competent individuals in the future. Integration of modern technology keeps education more modernized and is ready for the time change.